

Education Quality and Society

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Abstract- “Education is the foundation of a civilized society, so it becomes the duty of every person working in the education sector to increase the quality of education, whether it is to bring discipline in the field of child education or to include moral values for quality development in teacher education or to enhance the quality of education.”

Society is such an informal school where the child directly or indirectly learns many things. This community has an important role in any society in enhancing the quality of education. The child learns from the community in his society, ethics, etiquette, various customs and most importantly, how we should behave with cooperation etc. The child learns from the community in his society, ethics, etiquette, various customs and most importantly, how we should behave with cooperation etc. Through a society the student gets to learn many things in a practical way that he might not get to learn in school.

Quality education means the development of qualities or the inclusion of qualities in education so that the students and the objectives of education can be achieved well.

When we talk about quality in education, then we will consider such education as quality, which gives the benefit of that education to the students. A good educational quality occurs when the processes meet the needs of the individual and the society in general.

I. INTRODUCTION

Through a society, the student gets to learn many things in practical form, which he may not get to learn in school.-:

➤ *Developing social qualities*

Many social qualities are learned in any student by living in the society, the qualities of cooperation, sacrifice, collective interest, etc.

➤ *Character development of the student*

Only a good character makes a good citizen, it becomes very necessary that his character development should also be done in the child and this character development can be done well with the help of community or society.

➤ *Physical development*

A healthy mind lives in a healthy body and only with the help of a healthy mind we can do some creative creation, so it is very important to have a healthy body and with the help of a society and community, a student can learn do many

sports, yoga and physical development. In society activities are done for learning so that the physical development of the student takes place.

➤ *Professional Development*

If we have to give quality education to the students, then it is necessary that we give such education to the students by which they can become self-reliant and can also cooperate financially in the country. Students' get vocational training by living in the society, most of the members of the society are part of some business or business and when the children see these activities around them, they participate, they learn as well. Therefore, learning to learn things in practice, they gradually become skilled in doing things.

➤ *Sense of patriotism*

Only by living in a society, a student understands the importance of nation and the feeling of patriotism and what are his responsibilities towards the nation, what are his rights, a student is able to understand these things practically by staying in the society.

Education is the foundation of a civilized society, so it becomes the duty of every person working in the education sector to increase the quality of education, whether it is to bring discipline in the field of child education or to include moral values for quality development in teacher education or to enhance the quality of education. It becomes necessary to have some salient features within the people working in the field, so that the true meaning of education can be understood and explained.

A good and quality education is one that makes all students financially productive, enables them to develop sustainable livelihoods and also provides them with the necessary capabilities to enhance individual well-being to contribute to a peaceful and democratic society.

A good and high quality education is related to outcomes. The result is the peak performance of learning that occurs after completing an academic program.

It is the result of what the student learned while pursuing education.

And many measures have also been suggested to improve quality education by using result based education.

We should keep in mind the mission vision and objectives of the institute, what are the educational objectives of the program, should be taken care of the learning outcomes of the students, what will be the outcomes of the program, what will be the course outcomes,

What are the teaching methods, what are the tools of assessment and evaluation, Continuous quality improvement, Outcome based learning and student success Creative message exploration Presentation of results automated mind mapping etc. When students are given quality education then they will be able to come out of the cycle of poverty. A quality education underpins all hope beliefs. It also empowers people to live more healthy and sustainable lives. This era of Corona did not let education stop even in difficult times through high technology, so technical means have also played an important role to increase the quality of education.

Quality education is meant to be an education which is not given by memorization but on practical basis. And such education which is full of practical qualities, we understand such education as quality education. The quality of education means, in what quantity and with how much success education achieves its goals and objectives.

Any society or state determines the goals and objectives as per the needs of the citizens of its society and accordingly makes the system of education and if education is successful in achieving the objectives and goals as required by the state or society, then it is understood that. It is known that education is of quality.

To bring quality in education, it is necessary that the objectives of education should be built on the basis of physical, social, economic, cultural environment.

It is very important to have a proper environment for learning and for that it is very important to make the environment around the students conducive for learning and learning.

The main aim of education is the all-round development of the students and this is possible only when quality education is provided to the students.

Quality education is not that which is based only on knowledge, quality education is that which is practical. When a work includes all the qualities (practical and theoretical) related to that work, then it is seen and understood as the quality of that work and this aspect is also there in education.

When we talk about quality in education, then we will consider such education as quality which gives the benefit of that education to the students.

Therefore, it will be my endeavor that I can successfully achieve my objective with my research and my chosen subject. I can try to increase the quality of education even more by connecting the field of management and education.

At present, where students are probably getting all the modern means but their moral values are getting degraded, in such a situation we should not forget that education may be given by modern means but the rules of Gurukul period include moral values in it. Schools are the backbone of any society, so it is very important to run them systematically. Schools are broadly divided into two parts, Government

Schools and Private Schools, the complete management of government schools is in the hands of government and the management of private schools is completely in the hands of private entrepreneurs.

According to an analyst report for Education an estimated 1.75 crore students left government schools and took admission in private schools, and this figure shows that at present, middle and upper classes People are more attracted towards private schools. IN such a situation it becomes necessary that the private schools should be run in the best possible manner with the confidence with which parents enroll their children in these schools and when it comes to systematic or excellent operation, it should be done without management and its functions can't be possible.

II. CONCLUSION

The gap between the educational achievements of the students of government and non-government schools has to be bridged so that every class of person can get the highest education. Following the new national education policy seems to solve a lot of problems.

At present, the concept has been created by the society that children who study in government schools are not as qualified and children studying in private schools are eligible.

It is very necessary to refute this type of mentality by the society. Efficient running of school both private and government, makes quality education an absolute responsibility of a society.

Efficient running of both the schools, whether private or government, makes quality education an absolute responsibility. It is the duty of all the people prevailing in the society that every student should be made a good citizen by making them efficient.

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